

Title: Deep Learning for Edge devices

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State of the art algorithms for applications like face recognition, object identification and tracking utilize deep learning based models for inference. Edge based systems like security cameras and self-driving cars necessarily need to make use of deep learning to go beyond the minimum viable product. The core deciding factors for such edge based systems are power, performance and cost as these devices possess limited bandwidth, have zero latency tolerance and are constrained by intense privacy issues. The situation is further exacerbated by the fact that deep learning algorithms require computation of the order of tera-ops for a single inference at test time, translating to a few seconds per inference for some of the complex networks. Such high latencies are not practical for edge devices, which typically need real time response with zero latency. Additionally, Deep learning solutions are extremely compute intensive resulting in, on the edge devices not being able to afford deep learning inference. Deep learning is necessary to bring smartness and autonomy to the edge. We will demonstrate through examples like face recognition, object identification and object tracking how to develop optimized solutions that offer better performance and higher accuracy.

Biography

Siddha is a Deep Learning Data Scientist at Deep Vision Inc which she joined after graduation from Carnegie Mellon University with a Master's in Computational Data Science. Her work ranges from Visual Question Answering to Generative Adversarial Networks to gathering insights from CERN's petabyte scale data and has been published at top tier conferences like CVPR. She is a frequent speaker at Strata+Hadoop & Strata AI conferences and advises the Data Lab at NASA. Website: <http://sidgan.me/siddhaganju>